

A Curious Case of Gastroenteritis: Introduction and Approach to Diagnosis and Management

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Eosinophilic gastroenteritis is an extremely rare benign inflammatory disorder that affects the digestive tract predominantly the stomach and small intestine. It roughly affects 10 in 100,000 people. Due to its manifestations being protean, diagnosis of this condition poses a significant challenge to the clinicians, with evidence of the following three criteria required: Suspicious clinical symptoms, histologic evidence of eosinophilic infiltration in the bowel and exclusion of other pathologies with similar findings. Management of this condition is another debate because it is a chronic disorder which follows a relapsing course and requires maintenance therapy.

Case Report: We present a case of 42-year-old female, who got admitted with vague abdominal symptoms and sudden abdominal distension which were initially thought to be manifestations of tuberculosis. After a series of blood investigations, CT scans, pan endoscopy and a diagnostic laparoscopy which were not suggestive of TB, a diagnosis of Eosinophilic Gastroenteritis was made and the patient was then managed medically.

Keywords: Eosinophilic, Gastroenteritis, Diagnosis, Management

INTRODUCTION

Eosinophilic gastroenteritis (EG or EGE), also known as eosinophilic enteritis,^[1] is a rare and heterogeneous condition characterized by patchy or diffuse eosinophilic infiltration of gastrointestinal tissue, first described by Kaijser in 1937.^{[2][3]}

The disease is well known to be more common among the pediatric population, with the affected adults typically between the 3rd and 5th decade of life.^[4]

The disease follows a chronic and relapsing course. Any part of the GI tract can be affected, and isolated biliary tract involvement has also been reported.^{[5][6]} The stomach is the organ most commonly affected, followed by the small intestine and the colon.^{[7][8]}

According to Kleins classification, it is divided into three subtypes- mucosal, muscular and serosal and its manifestations are variable depending on the intestinal segment and layer involved.

Studies from the United States have found a prevalence ranging between 8.4 and 28 per 100000^[9,10], with a slightly increasing incidence over the past 50 years^[11]. The more recent estimates of EGE in the United States have found a shift from male preponderance^[12,13] to female predominance^[10]. Higher socioeconomic status, Caucasian race and excess weight may be risk factors of EGE^[11], and a possible hereditary component (genetic factor) is suggested by reports of familial cases^[14].

This can illustrate the importance of including EG in the differential diagnosis of abdominal pain even when there are no obvious allergens that suggest it as a possible reason.

CASE REPORT

Here we present a case of a 42-year-old female who is a known case of hypothyroidism and bronchial asthma on medications. She was on antitubercular therapy for 9 months after being diagnosed with TB lymphadenopathy 15 years ago. She came to the hospital with vague abdominal complaints like nausea, abdominal discomfort and sudden distension of abdomen since last 5 days. She had no complaints of vomiting, loose stools, fever, evening rise of temperature, cough, weight loss or any loss of appetite. She did not complain of any exacerbation of allergic manifestation in the recent past. She was vitally and hemodynamically stable and abdominal examination revealed distension.

Complete hemogram was done which revealed leucocytosis (21,660/cumm): neutrophils 75%, lymphocytes 12% and eosinophils 10%. All the other biochemical tests were normal.

USG abdomen and pelvis revealed free fluid in the abdomen suggestive of ascites.

CT Scan of the abdomen and pelvis revealed concentric mural thickening and mucosal edema of the small bowel loops more in the distal jejunum and ileum with concentric mural thickening of the visualised thoracic esophagus and gastroesophageal junction and moderate ascites likely inflammatory. There was evidence of mild chronic parenchymal liver disease.

These were followed by tapping of the ascitic fluid and an array of tests were done on the fluid to detect tuberculosis. GeneXpert, TB MGIT were negative, Adenosine deaminase was within normal limits (5 units/lit), and no other organism could be grown.

In order to get a tissue diagnosis, a panendoscopy was done which revealed pangastritis, duodenitis and prominent veins in the lower esophagus and biopsy taken was not suggestive of any malignancy, dysplasia, viral inclusions or amyloid deposition.

Finally a decision was taken to carry out a diagnostic scopy of the abdominal cavity, which turned out to be negative.

Serial hemograms revealed leucocytosis (20,900/cumm) in which eosinophils were on a rising trend (23%).

This raised a suspicion of some allergic etiology and serum IgE levels were done to confirm which were raised 5 fold (515.40 IU/ml).

A diagnosis of eosinophilic gastroenteritis was made and the patient was treated with steroids. The eosinophilic counts were reduced and the patient felt clinically better after the steroid treatment. She was discharged with oral budesonide and followed up regularly without any complaints of remission.

Figure 1: Panendoscopy

Both immunoglobulin E (IgE) dependent and delayed TH2 cell-mediated allergic mechanisms have been demonstrated to be involved in the pathogenesis of EGE. Interleukin 5 (IL-5) has also been shown to play an essential role in the expansion of eosinophils and their recruitment to the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, the mechanism underlying the pathogenic hallmark of EGE. Chemokines, namely eotaxin 1 and $\alpha 4\beta 7$ integrin, are also known to contribute to eosinophilic homing inside the intestinal wall. Other mediators-most notably IL-3, IL-4, IL-13, leukotrienes and tumor necrosis factor (TNF)-alpha-act to enhance eosinophilic trafficking and have been proposed to help in prolonging lymphocytic and eosinophilic activity^[26,27]. Many of these immune-related molecules are currently under consideration as potential targets for molecular therapy of EGE. Once recruited to the GI tract, the activated eosinophils induce a significant inflammatory response by secreting a variety of mediators including the cytotoxic granules that lead to structural damage in the infiltrated intestinal layers^[26]. Hypereosinophilia being the hallmark, maybe absent in 20% patients. However, hypoalbuminemia and other abnormalities are suggestive of malabsorption.

CT scans show nodular and irregular thickening of the folds in the distal stomach and proximal small bowel, The endoscopic appearance includes erythematous, friable, nodular, and occasional ulcerative changes.^[28]

Sometimes diffuse inflammation results in complete loss of villi, involvement of multiple layers, submucosal oedema and fibrosis.^{[29][30]} Definitive diagnosis involves histological evidence of eosinophilic infiltration in biopsy slides. Infiltration is often patchy, can be missed and laparoscopic full thickness biopsy may be required. Radio isotope scan using technetium (^{99m}Tc) exametazime-labeled leukocyte SPECT may be useful in assessing the extent of disease and response to treatment. Idiopathic hypereosinophilia should also be considered.

Corticosteroids are the mainstay of therapy with a 90% response rate. Appropriate duration of steroid treatment is unknown and relapse often necessitates long term treatment. Various steroid sparing agents e.g. sodium cromoglycate, ketotifen and montelukast have been proposed, with mixed results.^{[31][32]} Oral budesonide can be useful as well.^[33] An elimination diet may be successful if a limited number of food allergies are identified.^[34] An elemental diet may also be successful in the treatment of children.^[35] Iirentelimab was found to improve eosinophil counts and symptoms in individuals with eosinophilic gastritis and duodenitis.^{[36][37]}

None

CONCLUSION

EGE is a chronic GI disease, having protean manifestations that mimic many other GI disorders. Its diagnosis requires a combination of clinical and pathologic criteria that are evaluated upon suspicious laboratory, radiologic and endoscopic findings.

Although the association etiology and pathogenesis of EG remain unclear, there are studies suggesting that approximately 45%-63% of patients diagnosed with EG had a history of allergies, such asthma, rhinitis, drug, or food allergies; eczema; and parasitic infections,^{[38][39]} while others have found as an with other autoimmune conditions. The clinical manifestations of EG are not specific and hence diagnosis of EG pose a challenge.

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